

Effect of Coordination on the Psychopharmacological Activity of Chlordiazepoxide. Part-I. Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes

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Manuscript received 17 March 1994, accepted 22 March 1995

Chlordiazepoxide (7-chloro-2-methylamino-5-phenyl-3H-1,4-benzodiazepine-4-oxide) is an effective psychotherapeutic agent¹. Since coordination of biologically active compounds often results in enhanced biological activity, we report here the coordination compounds of chlorides, nitrates and acetates of divalent Cu and Zn chlordiazepoxide and the effect of coordination on the drug potential of the latter.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature, soluble in THF, DMSO and DMF and sparingly soluble in ethanol. Molar conductance data (2.42–4.02 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) reveal their covalent nature. Ethanolic solutions of the complexes do not give positive test for ionisable ions, which indicates that anions (i.e. chloro, acetato and nitro groups) have entered into the coordination sphere during complex formation reaction.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)		
	N	Cl	M
C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ O	13 80	11 80	
(White)	(14 0)	(11 83)	
CuL ₂ Cl ₂	11 48	19 29	8 60
(Green)	(11 45)	(19 32)	(8 66)
CuL ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	10 56	9 00	7 89
(Green)	(10 76)	(9 08)	(8 13)
CuL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	8 90	4 49	7 89
(Green)	(8 89)	(4 50)	(8 07)
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	11 40	19 35	8 80
(White)	(11 42)	(19 27)	(8 88)
ZnL ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂	10 67	9 20	8 42
(White)	(10 73)	(9 06)	(8 35)
ZnL ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	8 73	4 51	8 12
(White)	(8 87)	(4 49)	(8 28)

The elemental analysis and molecular weights data indicate metal : ligand ratio as 1 : 2 for all the complexes.

Chlordiazepoxide revealed ir bands at 1 310 (N–O stretch)², 945 (N–O band)³ and 3 340 cm⁻¹ (NH)⁴. The ν_{N-O} ligand band was found shifted (40–60 cm⁻¹) towards the lower side in all the complexes. This confirms the coordination of the ligand to the metal through the oxygen of N-oxide group. The δ_{N-O} band showed only a small nega-

tive shift (10–20 cm⁻¹) on complex formation. This is in fair agreement with the earlier reported views⁵. The ν_{NH} band shifted (40–50 cm⁻¹) towards the lower side in all the complexes. This confirms coordination of nitrogen of the N–H moiety of the ligand to the metal ion⁶.

Far-ir spectra revealed medium intensity bands in all the complexes. In the chloro complexes, three new bands were observed at 520–540 (M–O)⁷, 470–480 (M–N)⁸ and 330–350 cm⁻¹ (M–Cl)⁹. These bands confirm that (i) chlordiazepoxide is coordinated to the metal ion as bidentate ligand and (ii) the chloride ion is present in the coordination sphere of the metal ion, thus satisfying its primary and secondary valencies as well.

In the acetato complexes, a new medium intensity doublet observed at 490–520 cm⁻¹ is assignable to the two separate M–O stretching, one due to the metal-oxygen (of N-oxide group of chlordiazepoxide) and the other to the metal-oxygen (of the carboxylic group of acetate ion). The ν_s and ν_{as} frequencies corresponding to the carboxylic group of the acetate ion (respectively at 1 410 and 1 550 cm⁻¹) in the metal salts¹⁰ were found to be shifted in opposite direction upon complex formations. This confirms that acetate ions are bonded to the metal through C–O moiety of the carboxylic group as a unidentate ion¹¹ only.

Three additional sharp bands at 1 000, 1 250 and 1 420 cm⁻¹ observed in the nitrate complexes, are assigned to ν_2 , ν_1 and ν_4 modes of coordinating nitrate ions. Since the separation between the ν_4 and ν_1 band is 170 cm⁻¹ therefore, it confirms that the nitrate ions are coordinated in a unidentate manner¹². Medium intensity bands at 420 and 410 cm⁻¹ in these complexes are assignable respectively to M–N (nitrate) and M–N (methylamino) stretching vibrations¹³.

In the Cu^{II} complexes with 3d⁹ configuration, the predicted μ_{eff} values are >1.90 BM for tetrahedral and < 1.90 B.M. for square-planar and octahedral complexes¹⁴. In the present study, the μ_{eff} values for all the Cu^{II}-chlordiazepoxide complex were found in the range 1.8–2.21 B.M. These values correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron¹⁵. However no specific conclusion regarding the stereochemistry¹⁶ could be drawn merely on the basis of magnetic moment data. In electronic spectra, a

strong absorption band was observed at 14 150–14 410 cm^{-1} which is assignable to $T_{2g} \leftarrow E_g$ transition in a distorted octahedral field around copper ions having D_{4h} symmetry¹⁷.

Zn^{II} with $3d^{10}$ electronic configuration form diamagnetic complexes. The band observed at 26 230–26 340 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the Zn^{II} complexes may be due to either the intraligand transitions or due to metal-to-ligand charge transfer transitions only. However, octahedral structures are proposed for the complexes on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight and ir spectral studies.

Neuropharmacological activity : Muscle relaxant, taming, hypnotic and lethal effects were studied in mice. Pairs of mice in small cage were stimulated by electric shocks applied through a grid to the feet. This showed a marked irritability and fighting episodes. On treatment with chlordiazepoxide and the chloro complexes respectively, these mice had shown no compulsion to fight each other.

Hypnotic effects were produced in mice by two complexes below the lethal dose. Hypnotic dose HD_{50} has been defined as the dose which caused, in 50% of the mice, a loss of righting reflex, and the lethal dose LD_{50} has been defined as the dose which killed half of the mice. 'Margin of Safety' between the taming dose and the lethal dose was 7–9 for the Cu and Zn complexes respectively, as compared to 16 for the chlordiazepoxide. However, the complexes showed taming, muscle relaxant activity as well as the toxicity much higher than chlordiazepoxide. Table 2 shows the comparison of their pharmacological properties, i.e. muscle relaxant, taming, hypnotic and lethal effects in mice.

TABLE 2—PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Inclined screen	Fighting	Hyponotic effect	Toxicity
	ED_{50} mg/kg p.o.	ED_{50} mg/kg p.o.	HD_{50} mg/kg p.o.	LD_{50} mg/kg p.o.
Chlordiazepoxide (CNDO)	100	40	620	620
$[\text{CuCl}_2 \text{ CDNO}]$	60	25	260	250
$[\text{ZnCl}_2 \text{ CDNO}]$	70	30	200	300

*CDNO = chlordiazepoxide.

Experimental

Chlordiazepoxide (Wilson Laboratories, Bombay) was used after recrystallisation from aqueous solution. Metallic salts, solvents and other chemicals were of AnalaR grade

or used after recrystallisation. Molecular weight was determined as described earlier¹⁸.

Molar conductivity (0.001 M solution in nitrobenzene) was measured on a Systronix 321 conductivity bridge, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, magnetic moment on Gouy's balance and electronic spectra on a Hitachi spectrophotometer.

Metal salts (0.02 mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) were dissolved separately in ethanol to give saturated solutions. A mixture of the metal salt solution and the ligand solution was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled overnight in a refrigerator. The resulting crystallised complexes were filtered, washed with chilled ethanol and dried (80–85°), yields 55–62%.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (L.M.S.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the financial assistance.

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